

Interview Analysis With MAXQDA: Effect of Training on Organization Performance With Mediation of Employees Work Attitude in Textile Industries of Ethiopia

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Abstract – Global competitiveness based on the serious matter of work attitude of employee because it is dependent on when well companies train their work force. At the advent of technology, it is easy to investigate and improve the employee attitude towards work with the inclusion of technological for human upgrading through training. Training may be very from organization to organization in form of on job and off job. Training paved the way forward the type of attitude employee have towards their work. Skill labor positive view towards work is sub structured on advanced training methods that make them differentiate in workplace competition. Researchers first make thematic analysis in form of code data segment with help of MAXQDA 2020 software. After activation of all inserted interviewed, researchers were conducted the mixed method analysis. Single case analysis was framed for theme identification with help of thematic analysis. After that, thematic coding was framed for content analysis. For identification, screening and intent PRISMA was used employed. Coded frequency matrix was assimilated to depict the functionalism of training in the study area in the form of bibliographic analysis. Systematic evaluation of interviewed text manifested that training consider by most employees as the initial point of skill development and extended part of positive work attitude development, thus ended with enhanced organizational performance in textile industries. Study outcomes based on positivism approach will policy recommendations because of its objectivity.

Keywords: Training; Commitment; Work Attitude, Organization Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Companies can reap the training of providing training for their employees because well-trained workers help increase productivity and profits (Tortia et. al., 2022). In the present environment, training and development is the most important factor for the organizational success since it increases the efficiency and the effectiveness of both the employees and the organization (Shiferaw, 2022). Finding skills shortages on teams (such as a lack of expertise in a particular field) can affect each member's productivity. Employee trust can be increased and the period lost to misinterpretation and conflict can be decreased by team training in communication techniques, conflict resolution, and diversity and equity (Gupta, 2022).

Interview was conducted in the mid part of 2022. Researchers completed the all interview with in one month time at the textile industries located in industrial park (IPDC) Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. HR managers were

focused for qualitative data collection. This study focused on the interview interpretation of two textile industry; Aston and Aravid Company, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

Nowadays, one of the fundamental skills that will provide firms a competitive edge is best fit training, which is seen from a strategic skill based perspective. In particular, a new aspect of rivalry has been added to the races between companies vying for a larger piece of the market, at least in terms of intensity (Gobena & Kant, 2022). This struggle is regarding getting and retaining qualified skilled recruits (Kant & Asefa, 2022). Therefore, companies must be viewed as desirable employers by both prospective semi skilled employees and their current skilled employees (Danilwan & Dirhamsyah, 2022). When seen from this angle, it becomes clear that work attitude of employee practices serve to persuade potential trainees (Asefa & Kant, 2022; Jashari & Kutillovci, 2020). The efficient constitution of training has been initiated for the conceptual framework of the study. This section specifically mentions business responsibilities for locating potential candidates. The implementation procedures for employee commitment will be covered in the following phase (Otoo et. al., 2022). The relationship between the working approach, the result, and the employee commitment to human resources management will be conveyed in the final stage.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Training

The oldest type of training that has been recorded dates back to the prehistoric period and involved "on-the-job training," or teaching young people how to conduct adult tasks like hunting and fishing. In other terms, the "master" teaching the "novice" knowledge and skills. Training is the process of imparting knowledge and abilities that pertain to certain practical capabilities, either to oneself or to others (Boon et. al., 2019). Human resources management has a framework that is more focused on personnel management during that time because it previously had more static tasks to do. J.L. Moreno established role-playing in training for adults in 1930.

Role-playing was first used in adult education in 1930 by J.L. Moreno as a technique for preparing the student for greater competency in predicted circumstances. World War I introduced Job Instruction Training (JIT) in 1939. A supervisor or a designated coworker will train a new employee step-by-step using the job instruction approach as a type of straightforward on-the-job training. For jobs needing manual skills, like factory labor, this type of training was effective. With the advent of the computer and the internet in the 1980s, the first Computer Based Training (CBT) programs were introduced, and new e-learning tools and delivery techniques were invented and rapidly extended (Tanova & Bayighomog, 2022; Shiferaw, 2022).

Source: MAXQDA 2020 Output 2023

When Job Support was established in the 1990s, companies started employing e-learning to teach their staff. The new standard was to instruct adult learners on where to go for information to support their work performance (Saks, 2022). According to many definitions, training is an important part of modern business administration from this perspective. Cooke and others (2022) A structured setting where individuals are instructed and taught technical knowledge relevant to their professions is referred to as training. It focuses on instructing staff members on how to operate particular equipment or do particular jobs in order to boost productivity. The process of giving a person the necessary abilities to perform their work efficiently, expertly, and effectively is known as training. Employee training is not ongoing but rather occasional. Employee training is not ongoing; rather, it is periodic and provided at predetermined intervals. Typically training will be offered by an expert or professional in relevant field or work (Aguinis et. all, 2022).

The effectiveness of a staff member's talents is not the only thing that is impacted by training in an organization; emotional intelligence, time management skills, and a better attitude toward assigned work are also impacted (Amrutha and Geetha, 2020). Employees of the company benefit from training and development in that they take a more sophisticated approach to their work since they are more competent, do better work with fewer mistakes, and need less supervision. This improves the workers' attitude toward their work (Mammadova, 2022; Mohiuddin et. al., 2022).

Employees can benefit from training if they want to understand how their work fits within the structure, mission, and accomplishments of their firm. Employees can thus become more motivated and enthusiastic about their work as they realize how important what they do is to the success of the company (Chowdhury et. al, 2022). Work attitudes are influenced by a person's personality and organizational fit as well as the job's demands, how they view organizational justice and the psychological contract, how they interact with coworkers and managers, and how stressed out they are at work (Armstrong & Taylor, 2023). Professionals in training and development have a responsibility to create, implement, and assess the success of their programs in lowering conflicts over workplace performance. The association between training experiences and attitudes is investigated in this study. This study investigates the associations between training experiences, attitudes, and perceptions of work proficiency (Pramestari et. al, 2022). Faisal (2023) demonstrated that there is almost no direct evidence regarding firm training strategies based on representative samples of various employing organizations. Also, a number of scholars have argued that businesses that operate in competitive markets only provide the most complete training.

Training and development aids organizations in attracting and keeping top personnel, boosting morale and job satisfaction, boosting output, and increasing profits. Also, organizations with engaged staff report 41 percent lower absenteeism rates and 17 percent higher productivity (Garcia, et al., 2023). Employees that receive training gain better job-related skills and knowledge as well as increased self-assurance. They will perform better and operate more productively and efficiently as a result (Palmer & Winters, 1993). If courses, workshops, and self-study choices solve performance gaps, training improves organizational efficiency. Companies examine employee competencies using operational data, such as missed deadlines or product faults. This may involve collaboration, business acumen, or project management (Chapano et al., 2023).

Training appears to have a favorable impact on business outcomes through higher productivity, enhanced managerial abilities, decreased production costs, simple access to profits, and enlarged market (Hamouche, 2021; Collins, 2021; Garcia, et al., 2023).

Work attitude of employee

Employee work attitudes are the result of a three-stage process. Making a concrete commitment proposition in the first step awakens the notion that it is the greatest place to work. The second step involves making external marketing efforts to draw in the institution's top training. The final phase entails boosting loyalty and having faith in the pledge, according to an internal marketing study (Adula & Kant, 2020). Work attitude of employee refers to how applicants, both past and present, feel about the company. Work attitude of employee is investigated in three dimensions in order to scale these perceptions.

The training for well-known and well-known companies has been higher than that of unrecognized companies in the first dimension of being a well-known company. Positive company selection is the second factor. Businesses with a good selection are preferred to those with a bad selection. Employee image is the third dimension, which is described as the beliefs of job searchers (Mammadova, 2022). In order to be favored by candidates in job applications, using these dimensions to make a committed effort, constructing a suitable training channel, building trained manpower through this channel, and utilizing this sense of trained manpower, can create a successful image promotion (Nurhasanah et. al., 2023).

In conclusion, the actions of training determinants potential candidates and looking for and hiring employees are definitely influenced by the company's selection (Kant et. al., 2023). The compatibility between the individual and the organization is one of the key elements in the training determinants of the employee commitment. One of the main objectives of training is exactly this. These firms are more appealing to those individuals when they associate these attributes with the corporate image of the organization for which they are applying.

When seen from this angle, prospective employees favor companies that have a positive selection. Business scale, corporate social responsibility, and efficient use of social networks all contribute to a business's appeal (Tilman, 2021). According to some academics, more skilled job applicants will choose applying to companies with a strong commitment to their employees (Wata et. al., 2022). In addition, by improving business performance, well-planned work attitude of employee policies can save trainmen expenses (Nurhasanah et. al., 2023).

As a result, work attitude of employee practices play a crucial part in luring clients to businesses by cultivating a positive selection among the general public. By cultivating a positive selection and image among the general public, the Training plays a significant role in training and retaining customers (Kant et. al., 2023). It

should not be overlooked that the goal of work attitude of employee is to make the company appear to potential employees as a fantastic place to work (Tian et. al., 2020).

The correct set of skills and talents are acquired by employees through training and development, which enhances their performance. Training initiatives also assist staff members in changing their attitudes toward their work, which is a crucial component of enhancing performance. (Sugiarti et al., 2021) (Hamouche, 2021).

In general, employees with positive attitudes perform better, whereas those with negative attitudes perform less than optimally. According to Mira et al., managers are responsible for keeping an eye on staff attitudes and dealing with issues like negativity and laziness (2020). Training new hires has recently gotten a lot of attention and is seen as a competitive advantage for firms, according to Capia et al. (2021). Training new hires has recently gotten a lot of attention and is seen as a competitive advantage for firms, according to Capia et al. (2021). The employee commitment serves a critical function in helping the institution achieve its goal of attracting applicants by positioning companies at a certain point in time.

Any higher education institution or company that wants to thrive in the diverse and complex economy of today has found it essential to engage in continual training and development in order to increase production proficiencies and get the best return on the investment of human capital. Although training is a crucial component of the employer–employee relationship and although this aspect of training efficacy is seems very crucial (Ababneh, 2021). This suggests that an employee's work ethic and training methods.

Although performance of employees is one of the key metrics that the top management emphasizes, employees are more focused on their own productivity and are becoming more conscious of the information and abilities that are rapidly becoming obsolete in their volatile environment. According to the literature, good training and development will make employees better positioned for professional advancement since increased career possibilities increases personal motivation (Meijerink et. al., 2021). In this case, the corporation will teach highly skilled applicants by utilizing the employee value proposition through training as a tool to improve employee work behavior (Ciobanu et. al., 2019).

According to a survey conducted by Ababneh (2021) among 1,600 human resources professionals from various industries, employee commitment is at the top of the list of new methods to invest in training determinants trained people. According to human resources management, employee commitment comprises and integrates elements like skilled labor and training of skilled employees, development, motivation, and adaptability with relation to target populations (Hamouche, 2021).

Mira et al. (2020) claimed that because these training are rare, valuable, hard to reproduce, and hard to replace, organizations should be more successful at attracting, selecting, and maintaining them. The Conference Board and The Economist performed research on 23 employee commitments, and the three main advantages they discovered were better trained workforce, retention, and training determinants (Meijerink et. al., 2021).

3. RESEARCH AND METHODOLOGY

This study sought to determine what aspects of employee work attitudes are taken into account by organizations' human resource procedures for employee training. The process of developing human resources with a positive work attitude was studied as a case study, and qualitative analysis was used.

Ten human resources managers, from Aston and Arvind textile industry positioned in Ethiopia capital city Addis Ababa; Ethiopia were interviewed in-depth for this exploratory and descriptive study. The evaluations of

these studies have been taken into account. A wide range of research has been used to assess the effectiveness of business locations in luring prospective applicants to the institution.

Content analysis was one of the qualitative analytical methods used in this investigation. Since they provide the opportunity to conduct in-depth one-on-one interviews with the data, focus groups are preferred in sampling due to their methodical structure (Tilman, 2021). A semi-structured in-depth interview technique was used for this study by adhering to the pre-planned interview flow. The semi-structured interview technique was employed to collect data for the study because, by using pre-made interview forms, it enabled human resources managers to express their opinions about the employee commitment process in a more organized way. This approach has been beneficial in that it provides the interviewer with a certain level of consistency and flexibility (Gaber, 2020).

In-person meetings held between July and December of 2022. Interview forms were created and recorded over papers due to the companies' directions procedure in order to prevent data loss. The data was evaluated using MAXQDA 2020, one of the computer-aided qualitative data analysis programs. The computer ensured that the interview texts followed a predetermined structure. The MAXQDA 20 application systematizes content analysis and makes it simple to examine several texts at once. The program received praise for its applicability, in-depth analysis of the texts, sound data management, in-depth examination of the subject matter, and in-depth relationship between concepts.

CODE MATRIX BROWSER

Code System	Arvind 1	Arvind 2	Arvind 3	Arvind 4	Arvind 5	Ashton 1	Ashton 2	SUM
HRM PRACTICES						■		1
EMPLOYEE WORK ATTITUDE	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	22
REWARD	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	31
Performance Appraisal	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	24
Training	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	7
Training plan	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	7
Training Type	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	7
Training Area	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	8
Training effect on work attitude	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	7
Training Effect on Organization Perform	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	7
Recruitment	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	28
Organizational performance	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	34
SUM	26	26	26	26	26	27	26	183

Source: MAXQDA 2020 output (2023)

The program received praise for its applicability, in-depth analysis of the texts, sound data management, in-depth examination of the subject matter, and in-depth relationship between concepts. Tables and statistics for the analysis were produced by coding the interviews with human resources managers. Coding is a programmatic method for carefully analyzing and categorizing documents (MAXQDA, 2020).

IMPLICATIONS

The data from the audio recordings of the interviews with human resources managers were encoded and fed into the MAXQDA 2020 programme in order to uncover themes, arrange themes, define the findings, and interpret the findings. According to professional advice, coding was created using the code key and specified in the programme. The meanings of each interview text, such as a word, sentence, or paragraph, were studied and coded. The interview findings were organized into texts and read one at a time in order to be able to code. The differences between the same codes across individuals or between sectors were then established by taking into account the linkages between the codes. The coding groups and then the data were arrived at using the identified partnerships. Interviews with managers of human resources were moved to the MAXQDA 2020 package software. The codes containing the elements in each interview were examined at the level of the interview's words, phrases, and paragraphs. The interviews in figure 1 were analyzed on a code basis.

Fig -1: Coding for Employee Training Questions
Source: MAXQDA 2020 output (2023)

As seen in Figure 1, the coding-related MAXQDA single case model map has been created. The interview forms that were collected as a consequence of the interviews were evaluated to create the codes. A single case model map was generated using the fundamental codes that the words, sentences, and paragraphs in the text were associated with during reading after the codes and interview forms were uploaded to the MAXQDA qualitative research package programme. It can be noted that "training" and "work attitude " coding are predominate as a consequence of the interviews performed in accordance with the single case model map displayed in Figure 2. Figure 2 displayed the codes' distribution order for the question 2 types of training program prepared for employee.

Question 1: Based on question ET1 what are the types of training program prepared for employee?

Single-Case Model (Code Hierarchy)

Source: MAXQDA 2020 output (2023)

Answer: The Company provided training on the topic for new recruited employee the company provided induction training provided details about various work groups and the extent of cooperation within the company.

For staff member the supervisor prepares need assessment and skill gap assessment train their team.

In addition to that some training was provide collaboration with NGO like health and safety, personal hygiene, compliant handling.

Question 2: What criteria used to choose employee's for particular training program?

Single-Case Model (Code Hierarchy)

Source: MAXQDA 2020 output (2023)

Answer: Training is providing according to employee's job assignment that means after employee's recruitment he/she take induction training about the job and company rule and regulation and working environment.

The second base on skill gap assessment training proved for employees. In addition, for machine operator the company prepare training program according to educational back ground and skill.

On the other hand, the employees are selected for training by their supervisor according to their involvement and commitment.

Question 3: How the provided training for employees improves employee's work attitude?

Single-Case Model (Code Hierarchy)

Source: MAXQDA 2020 output (2023)

Answer Yes, training is increase employee performance and improves their employee's work attitude. After training employee's motivation and commitment is increase. The effectiveness of a staff member's talents is not the only thing that is impacted by training in an organization; emotional intelligence, time management skills, and a better attitude toward assigned work are also impacted.

Creative Coding

Source: MAXQDA 2020 output (2023)

Employees of the company benefit from training and development in that they take a more sophisticated approach to their work since they are more competent, do better work with fewer mistakes, and need less supervision.

Attitudinal training aims to convince or influence someone to make a choice within the preferred trend. It could entail altering attitudes along with related emotions, ethics, inspiration, along with attitude. The effectiveness of a staff member's talents is not the only thing that is impacted by training in an organization; emotional intelligence, time management skills, and a better attitude toward assigned work are also impacted. Positivity training and positive work attitude is advantageous to both the employee and the business. More enjoyment, fulfillment, and productivity are the results. While employers should support and encourage positive outlooks among their staff, in the end, it is up to the individual staff members to bring positive outlooks to the workplace.

Question 4: How training increase performance of organization?

Single-Case Model (Code Hierarchy)

Source: MAXQDA 2020 output (2023)

Answer Training is increasing the organization performance because it improves their skill and also the employees understand their problem improve their behavior, attitudinal, perception toward their work.

Improve employee's team spirit, communication and commitment. Through training, workers can develop new skills, polish those they already have, perform better, boost productivity, and become better leaders. Organizations should exert every effort to ensure that individuals perform at their highest levels because a firm is the culmination of what each employee accomplishes on an individual basis.

CODED FREQUENCY CHART:

Chart -1: Coded Frequency

Source: MAXQDA 2020 output (2023)

Researchers founded coded frequency chart as output of MAXQDA 2020 output. Coded frequency chart as output manifested that work attitude was the most profound determinants among other codes with a highest frequency of 44.2%. Which depicted that presence of work attitude intensify the relation between training and performance of organization. Thus work attitude have the potential to mediate the relation between training and performance of organization.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The results of this study indicate that there is a considerable correlation between an organization's work attitude of employee and prospective of training. Work attitude of employee practices play a significant part in firm selection of skilled and trained workforce, making them one of the most crucial factors to take into account when implementing training practices. The study's findings have led to a better understanding of how organizations can use employee commitment and effective external communication to draw in skilled workers. It has been observed that this connection promotes corporate selection, which has significantly increased the company's labor law as well as in the training.

Beside with offering long-term high corporate performance of firms, the emphasis on drawing the employee commitment to inspired employees is considered as an important consequence. In terms of generalization, the research's qualitative nature can be taken into account within its bounds. However, it is also possible to view the research's coverage of a specific time frame as a constraint. This study makes a serious forecast regarding the training factors that candidates will consider when selecting an employer, which can give companies that compete in the human resources market a competitive edge.

Companies must use outside personnel for specialized training even if their human resources strategy often favors' internal on job training. These on job training cadres are typically the places where strategic choices

are made and where management-level competence is needed. In these and comparable positions, there can be a critical vacancy that needs to be addressed right away. They must now employ the external assignment mechanism. Businesses can maintain their competitive advantages by quickly training determinants significant managerial job deficits to the institution with effective employee training and work attitude practices. This will affect economic growth, ensure the continuity of the process, and ensure the effectiveness of strategic decisions made. It is advised that real sector firms pay attention to employee training practices as a result of this study in order to draw skilled human resources to the organization. In academic investigations, it is advised to use quantitative approaches to fill in any potential gaps in order to make the research generalizable.

FUTURE RESEARCH AGENDA

Contributors to the qualitative interview analysis offer brief interview analysis of 10 HR managers of training department in order to pave forward the way for future research. Each comprehensive interview on training practices reveals the research knowledge's strengths and shortcomings, sketches out the field's key intellectual limits, and describes the present and upcoming research goals and how they will be addressed. The current study provides a clear and thorough assessment of the interviewed primary data that is currently accessible on training for beginning researchers. Furthermore, a qualitative evaluation of the interviews identifies research implications in the area of training practices that need to be filled.

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LIMITATIONS

If you start Stats from within a MAXQDA project file, only the first 1,000 variables and codes will be transferred to Stats. If you open an external file a maximum of 1,000 variables will be imported. Qualitative research has many limitations which include possible small sample sizes, potential bias in answers, self-selection bias, and potentially poor questions from researchers. Rigor is more difficult to maintain, assess, and demonstrate. The volume of data makes analysis and interpretation time consuming. The researcher's presence during data gathering, which is often unavoidable in qualitative research, can affect the subjects' responses.

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